

Open Source Community Building Guide

Introduction

Building a successful open-source community requires a strategy and level investment similar to building a successful product or application. The creator of that community must be strategic in identifying who their contributors are, why they contribute, and what resources they need to overcome the many barriers and challenges to successfully contributing to any open source project.

This guide outlines a comprehensive methodology for defining project goals, understanding contributor motivations, and creating a clear pathway for engagement. Drawing on best practices from the Mozilla Open Leadership Training Series and The Turing Way, this guide aims to help project maintainers foster a vibrant and sustainable open-source community. Below you will find guidelines for developing a strategy to growing your community as well as specific instructions for gathering the evidence needed to identify specific roadblocks to contribution.

Defining General Goals

Establishing clear goals is the foundation of any successful community-building effort. This begins with defining the project's vision and mission.

1. Project Vision and Mission:

- **Vision:** Articulates the long-term impact and aspirations of the project. For example, "To create a widely-used open-source tool that democratizes access to data analysis."
- **Mission:** Outlines the immediate goals and objectives, such as developing user-friendly features, building comprehensive documentation, and fostering a welcoming community.

2. Specific Objectives:

- **Goals:** Set measurable outcomes, such as "Increase the contributor base by 30% in one year."
- **Milestones:** Identify key achievements to track progress, like the release of major features or achieving community growth benchmarks.

Identifying Contributors and Their Incentives

Once your general goals are defined, you must understand what sort of contributors you need to achieve that goal. Understanding who your contributors are and what motivates them is crucial for building a thriving community. This involves identifying different types of contributors and their respective motivations.

1. Contributor Personas:

- **Types of Contributors:** Developers, documenters, designers, community managers, etc.
- **Demographics:** Background, skill level, interests.

2. Motivations and Incentives:

- **Intrinsic Motivations:** Personal growth, learning opportunities, passion for the project.
- **Extrinsic Motivations:** Recognition, monetary rewards, career advancement.

For instance, a developer might be motivated by the need to add specific functionality for their use case. At the same time, a technical writer may be more incentivized to contribute better documentation to onboard their teammates..

Understanding the Contribution Pathway

The contribution pathway outlines the stages through which individuals engage with the project, from first hearing about it to taking on leadership roles. Each stage has specific objectives and actions to facilitate smooth transitions.

I. Discovery:

- **Objective:** Identify how potential contributors first hear about the project or group.
- **Actions:**
 - Promote the project through social media, blogs, conferences, and collaborations.
 - Ensure a strong online presence with SEO-optimized content and listings on popular repositories.

II. First Contact:

- **Objective:** Understand how potential contributors first engage with the project.
- **Actions:**
 - Provide clear, welcoming landing pages and contribution guidelines.
 - Maintain responsive communication channels and host introductory community calls.

III. Participation:

- **Objective:** Facilitate how contributors first participate or contribute.
- **Actions:**
 - Label issues for beginners and offer detailed contribution guides.

- Assign mentors to new contributors and recognize their initial contributions publicly.

IV. Sustained Participation:

- **Objective:** Ensure ongoing involvement from contributors.
- **Actions:**
 - Regularly check in with contributors and invite them to community events.
 - Provide advanced contribution opportunities, continuous learning resources, and recognition.

V. Networked Participation:

- **Objective:** Promote networking within the community.
- **Actions:**
 - Host community events and encourage collaborative projects.
 - Establish mentorship programs and maintain active online community spaces.

VI. Leadership:

- **Objective:** Facilitate contributors taking on additional responsibilities or leadership roles.
- **Actions:**
 - Define pathways to leadership roles and involve contributors in decision-making.
 - Publicly recognize leadership contributions and provide platforms for leaders to share insights.

Conducting Interviews

Conducting thorough interviews is essential to gather evidence and identify archetypal contributors and their pathways. Generally, these interviews should be semi-formal, allowing subjects to provide evidence about their personal experiences in project contributions. These interviews should simultaneously provide evidence of an ideal contribution experience and the problems that hinder project contribution.

Interview Preparation:

1. Stakeholder Identification: Identify key stakeholders, including maintainers, active contributors, potential contributors, and users. These diverse perspectives provide a comprehensive view of the project's ecosystem.

2. Questionnaire Development: Develop focused questions for each stage of the contributor pathway and identify issues faced in contribution. The questions may vary highly depending on the individual's background and relation to the project. It is important for those conducting interviews to be flexible in their approach towards contributor interviews to allow for the most useful findings. A selection of questions for each stage is below.

Example Questions:

- **Discovery:**
 - "How did you first hear about our project?"
 - "What made the project stand out to you?"
- **First Contact:**
 - "Describe your initial interaction with our project."
 - "What resources or guidance were helpful initially?"
 - "What challenges did you face in your first interaction?"
- **Participation:**
 - "What was your first contribution?"
 - "How easy was it to find beginner tasks?"
 - "What difficulties did you encounter during your first contribution?"
 - "What obstacles did you face when trying to make your first contribution after initial contact?"
 - "Did you receive adequate support for your first contribution?"
- **Sustained Participation:**
 - "What motivates you to continue contributing?"
 - "How do you find and select ongoing tasks?"
 - "What improvements could make continued participation easier?"
 - "What challenges did you face in becoming a regular contributor?"
 - "What resources or support helped you to continue contributing?"
- **Networked Participation:**
 - "How have you connected with other contributors?"
 - "What networking opportunities or resources are most useful to you?"
 - "What difficulties did you encounter when networking with others?"
 - "How can the project better facilitate contributor networking?"
- **Leadership:**
 - "What does project leadership look like in your role?"
 - "What support did you receive to become a leader?"
 - "What challenges have you faced in leadership?"
 - "What barriers did you face moving to a leadership role?"
 - "What additional support would have made this transition smoother?"

Interview Execution:

Choose an appropriate format for conducting the interviews, such as one-on-one interviews for in-depth insights, focus groups for collective discussions, or online surveys for broader reach. Ensure accurate data collection by recording responses and taking detailed notes. This helps capture nuanced insights and direct quotes that can enrich the analysis.

Examples:

- **One-on-One Interviews:** Provide detailed, personal insights.
- **Focus Groups:** Enable dynamic interactions and collective brainstorming.

- **Online Surveys:** Gather data efficiently from a larger pool of respondents.

Data Collection:

Use digital tools like recording apps for one-on-one interviews and focus groups. Ensure survey questions are clear and concise, with options for open-ended responses.

Data Analysis

Analyze the qualitative data by identifying common themes and patterns across different interviews. Group similar responses to identify major themes, such as "onboarding challenges" or "community support." Where applicable, perform quantitative analysis to derive metrics and statistics that provide a broader view of the data. For example, calculate the percentage of contributors who discovered the project through specific channels or measure the average time from discovery to first contribution among different groups.

Creating the Community Building Roadmap

With the findings from the interviews, synthesize the key insights and prioritize actionable recommendations by developing Community Roadmap. The roadmap should be informed by thorough research and data collection, including interviews with key stakeholders. Below is a detailed narrative on creating a community building roadmap, incorporating insights from the attached Open@RIT presentation template.

1. Synthesis of Findings:

Begin by synthesizing the findings from the interviews and other data collection efforts. This involves summarizing the main insights and identifying key themes and patterns that emerged.

Key Insights:

- Common challenges in onboarding new contributors.
- Effective strategies for maintaining sustained participation.
- Opportunities for enhancing networked participation and leadership development.

Actionable Recommendations: Prioritize steps based on the evidence collected. For instance, if many contributors highlighted the need for better documentation, prioritize improving the quality and accessibility of the project's documentation.

2. Roadmap Development:

Develop a comprehensive roadmap that outlines both short-term actions and long-term strategies. This roadmap should be flexible enough to adapt to new insights and feedback from the community.

Short-Term Actions: Focus on immediate steps to address critical issues identified in the research. Examples include:

- **Improving Documentation:** Enhance guides and resources to support new contributors.
- **Onboarding Programs:** Implement mentorship programs to assist first-time contributors.
- **Community Events:** Organize virtual meetups and webinars to engage with the community.

Long-Term Strategies: Plan for sustainable growth and development of the community over time. Examples include:

- **Leadership Development:** Create pathways for contributors to take on leadership roles.
- **Networking Opportunities:** Facilitate connections among contributors through community forums and collaborative projects.
- **Continuous Learning:** Provide ongoing educational resources and training sessions.

3. Implementation Plan:

Detail the resources required, such as tools, personnel, and budget, to implement the roadmap effectively. Establish a clear timeline with milestones and deadlines to track progress and ensure accountability.

Resources Required:

- **Tools:** Collaboration platforms like Slack or Discord, project management tools, and documentation software.
- **Personnel:** Community managers, mentors, and technical writers.
- **Budget:** Allocate funds for community events, promotional activities, and tool subscriptions.

Timeline: Set specific milestones to mark progress and keep the community building efforts on track. Examples of milestones include:

- **Month 1:** Launch improved documentation and onboarding guides.
- **Month 3:** Host the first virtual community meetup.
- **Month 6:** Establish a mentorship program and assign mentors to new contributors.
- **Month 12:** Review and assess the progress of the community building initiatives.

Example: Open@RIT Community Building Roadmap

[Open@RIT Presentation Template](#)

Continuous Improvement and Evaluation

To ensure the ongoing success of your community-building efforts, establish mechanisms for continuous improvement and evaluation. Define key performance indicators (KPIs) to track progress and conduct regular reviews, such as quarterly or bi-annual assessments. Create a feedback loop to continuously collect input from the community and adapt the roadmap based on new evidence.

By following this structured, evidence-based methodology, you can effectively build and sustain a vibrant open-source community.